

TYG INDEX A NEW MARKER FOR PREDICTING CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES AND INSULIN RESISTANCE IN WOMEN WITH PM AND EM

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Purpose of the study. To determine insulin resistance by calculating the TyG index to determine the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases in women with PM (premature menopause) and EM (early menopause).

Materials and methods of research. The material for the study was blood samples that were involved in the study. The research methods were to determine the glycemic profile, TyG index, lipid profile, and CRP (seroreactive protein). To determine the effectiveness of treatment methods, patients with PM and EM were divided into 3 groups. The first group included 27 patients who were treated with MHT, the second group included 30 patients who were prescribed dosed physical activity, phytoestrogens and inositol, third group included 27 patients who refused all treatment methods.

Research results. In our study, it was interesting to determine the main trigger of the metabolic syndrome – insulin resistance by calculating an indirect indicator-the TyG index, which was higher than the reference values in all the studied groups of women. This index is also a strong predictor of the development of cardiovascular complications.

The metabolic profile also showed positive changes women with recovery programs and negative dynamics in women without therapy. The glycemic profile in all women before therapy was within the normal range and had a significant tendency to reduce the level of glucose in the blood serum, but in women without therapy, a shift in the average blood sugar index to the values of the highest limit of normal was noted during 6 months of follow-up and amounted to 6.1 ± 0.2 mmol/l. TYG index also tended to decrease after treatment measures were taken. So, after MHT, the indicator reached the threshold value (4.49) and amounted to 4.44 ± 0.14 , which indicates the absence of insulin resistance in women, while after complex alternative therapy, the effectiveness was 7.4%, the indicator decreased, but did not reach the threshold value, which indicates the correct choice of therapy (a decrease in the TyG index from 5.01 ± 0.16 up to 4.64 ± 0.15) and the need to continue the initiated integrated approach. In the group without therapy,

this indicator did not tend to significantly change, which indicates that insulin resistance persists in women with PM and EM.

Dyslipidemia, manifested in hypertriglyceridemia, a decrease in HDL and an increase in LDL, was observed in almost all the studied women with PM and EM. The methods of treatment carried out made it possible to normalize the lipid spectrum of the blood with the achievement of indicators to the level of reference values. This was once again proved by a significant decrease in AC (atherogenicity coefficient) in group 1 by 13.7% and in group 2 by 12.1%, with absolute averages of 4.4 ± 0.14 and 3.77 ± 0.12 , which indicates the expediency of continuing the chosen tactics of managing women with PM and EM.

Conclusion. The prognostic reduction in the risk of cardiovascular diseases, manifested in a decrease in CRP values, was achieved more (a decrease of 18.2% from the baseline values) in the MHT group and by 7.8% in the 2nd therapeutic group.

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